

Why novel theoretical research on the possible topology of single elementary particles at rest is the next logical step and of paramount importance for the discovery of new physics beyond the Standard Model and the research in very high energies?

Why Quantum Topology research of single Elementary particles is important for the future of quantum new physics beyond the Standard model?

We strongly believe that extending our view of Quantum Topology not only for many bodies systems as a collection of particles interaction but also for single isolated elementary particles research, will become of paramount importance in the future and the next logical step we must take in order to discover new physics beyond the standard model that will provide all the missing information we need to decipher the yet unsolved mysteries like dark matter, dark energy and why there is more normal matter than antimatter, the hierarchy problem, what is vacuum space and so on and in general progress physics in all levels.

However in order to take the next step in very high energy physics theoretical research and phenomenology a *paradigm shift* is needed from our current dimensionless points-little spheres model to more sophisticated topologies and even manifolds describing effectively elementary and composite particles.

Why? What are the advantages in that for very high energy physics research and why this is the physical evolution of the research?

We were in good footing with QM at the beginning and the points and little spheres were initially adequate to (or little bumps in QFT...doesn't matter) to reduce the zoo of initially discovered particles to a relative few in the SM including the necessary Higgs Boson but now that we must go deeper and probe smaller and smaller distances, the little points-spheres ontology start to fail and we are forced to invent new points and spheres every time to explain these new phenomena. So now the SM gets inflated again!!

(see recently announced potential promising discovery from CERN about leptoquarks, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.11769> , <https://www.scinexx.de/news/technik/indizien-fuer-neue-physik-erhaerten-sich/> , <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qR6P0aRqYf8>).

This however will lead to a loss in *reductionism* of the theory and SM complicating things and potentially lead to a second era of a zoo of new subatomic particles.

This can be avoided however by this paradigm shift for very high energies quantum research of elementary particles by assigning an effective topology and even if possible manifold to these particle quanta and depart from their rather simplistic current or non-existing at all topology.

The advantages are obvious. All particles could be unified under a few numbers of **conformal topologies** and possible manifolds producing the intrinsic properties and known values of the particles and they decay thus transmutation from one particle to the other can be shown as simple topological transformations. This new physics beyond the SM for elementary particles new framework will have much more unifying power and also would provide us with critical new information and insight of the mechanics of single isolated elementary particles very high energy physics and how these properties are producing the measured know values of these particles.

The SM will be left intact and still holding as the best framework we have for the relative lower energies but a **topological paradigm shift** for very high energy physics describing single isolated elementary quanta we regard as necessary. This proposed new topological framework would also provide useful feedback to the SM and vice versa. **There is no reason to believe yet by any theory and experiment so far that the *probabilistic nature* of a collection of quantum particles interaction (i.e. measurement) are an inherent property from the single isolated particle case and also intrinsic to the single quantum elementary particles.**

As Nobel laureate Gerard 't Hooft has many time described, there is no reason to believe that the mechanics in very high energies cannot be *deterministic*. Therefore, elementary particles can have a topology and a dynamic energy flow manifold which are by definition deterministic concepts and structures. The possible deterministic nature of single isolated closed system elementary particles are also strongly **inferred** from our consistent experience of measuring very accurately the fixed values of their intrinsic properties like spin, charge, mass, magnetic moment etc. **If ontologically, single elementary particles would be probabilistic in nature then why are we measuring these same exact values every time we measure them?**

This surely implies deterministic *mechanics* and the SM model do not give answer of what an isolated elementary particle mechanics would be?

But in order to go to the next step of high energy physics research today and try fully to understand the quantum world and in extension macroscopic and produce a possible *complete quantum theory*, we cannot anymore **avoid** asking these questions about the intrinsic mechanics of elementary particles. Issues which could be easily investigated by assigning effectively a topology and dynamic manifold to the single elementary particles.

[Under this context and field of research described above, comes also our pioneering current research we present for peer-review to the physics community.](#)

Summary of our presented research:

We believe that we have reached in high energy physics a stage today where we cannot further ignore the possibility of a possible topology embedded on elementary single isolated particles which could explain and could be the missing information we desperately needed in order to take the next step for new physics beyond the SM at the very high energies theoretical research and therefore progress knowledge in the field. What we have done in our presented research was essentially to macroscopically using a physical sensor to emulate the free electron's at rest, magnetic flux field (i.e. emulation thus quantum simulation of particles not by s/w but by using real time other physical systems that mimic the behavior of the particle) and from that observation to extrapolate in 3D Euclidean space plus temporal coordinates, a dynamic topology and manifold for the **electron**.

Then via semi-classical analysis and Wolfram simulation of the differential geometry complying with the Lorentz group we have fine tuned the dynamic manifold of the proposed topology for the electron with its known intrinsic values like spin, charge, magnetic moment etc. and their related energies and were able to show that it produces the predicted values of QM and the standard model. Any slight variation of the proposed model values to the reported experimentally or theoretically predicted by QM in the literature, we have justified due the fact that our model refers to the ideal case of a completely isolated single electron and closed system. Also our *dynamic 4-dimesional* (3 spatial pus one temporal) *manifold* also mimics the 720° rotation, characteristic of all fermions. Finally, we have conclusively shown that our novel 4-spinor twisting loop topology can produce the measured properties of the single electron and mimic its behavior. Therefore a deterministic model explaining the behavior of a single isolated closed system, electron at very high energies is possible.

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